

A Case Study of Key Frame Extraction in Video Processing

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Abstract: Video is an integral part of our everyday lives and in too many fields such as content-based video browsing, compression, video analysing, etc., Video has a complex structure that includes scene, shot, and frame. One of the fundamental techniques in content-based video browsing is key frame extraction. In general, to minimize redundancy the key frame should be representative of the video content. A video can be more than one keyframes. The utilization of key frame extraction method speeds up the framework by choosing fundamental frames and thereby removing additional computation on redundant frames. Key frame extraction significantly reduces the video processing overhead time and increase the throughput. In this paper different types of key frame extraction methods are compared with their advantages and disadvantages.

Keywords: Key frame extraction; Content-based video; Video processing

I. INTRODUCTION

Video is the most powerful multimedia with which to capture the world around us. But the application of videos such as storing, retrieving, indexing and summarizing became very difficult nowadays. To resolve these problems key frame extraction technique is mainly used. Key frames are those frames that have the video's rich content. Video may describe as a visual representation of the data. Videos can be arranged as scene sequence, scenes as shots series, and shots as frame sequence.. Key frames are the frames which can represent the salient content and information of the shot. The key frames extracted will summarize a video's characteristics, and all of the key frames in the time series will control the image characteristics of a video. A simple rule for extracting key frames is that key frame extraction will rather be incorrect than not appropriate. So it is necessary to eliminate the repetitive information during key frame extraction.

Video: A video is a series of scenes

Scene: A scene is a logical collection of shots that take place through a semantic unit

Shot: A shot is a series of frames in one continuous movement taken by a single camera

Frames: A frame is created by pixels

Fig 1. Video to frame convert

II. KEY FRAME EXTRACTION

Key Frame Extraction plays an important role in many applications for video processing, such as video compression, recovery, skimming, editing etc. each described as an unbroken sequence of frames taken from a single camera that forms the video building block. Key Frame Extraction typically involves selecting one Frame to properly reflect in its cluster should obey two key principles.

First it should be fairly close to the frames in its cluster and second it should vary tolerably from frames in other clusters. First, a series of features are extracted from each frame in a standard key Frame Extraction process to form a feature vector. Next, to analyze the similarity / dissimilarity between frames, an effective measure of distance is applied to the feature vectors.

Eventually, shot and cluster boundaries are identified, and the main frames are extracted based on the distance measurement in the selected function space. These frames are very useful for object identification and for keeping track of the particular object.

III. CLASSIFICATION

Key frame extraction methods Broadly classified in two categories.

- a) Object Based Video Segmentation
- b) Shot Based Video Segmentation.